

Introduction of Deadlock: and its Conditions, Prevention, Avoidance, Detection, Recovery

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Abstract:

Deadlock is a circular wait condition that occur in multiprogramming, multiprocessing or distributed computer system. In multiprocessing environment, allocation of resources can become a point of conflict. Such conflict may lead the system into a state known as deadlock. Deadlock detection and recovery is one of the major challenges faced by distributed system. Also, various conditions may help prevent deadlock to some extent but to completely eradicate deadlock from the system an efficient operating system needs to be developed with efficient synchronization algorithms.

Keywords: Deadlock, circular wait, mutual exclusion, hold and wait, banker's algorithm, resource allocation.

i) INTRODUCTION

Deadlock can be defined formally as follows:

A set of process is deadlocked if each process in the set is waiting for an event that only another process in the set can cause.

A deadlock is a condition or situation in which two processes sharing the same resources are effectively preventing each other from accessing the ease to function. The earliest computer operating system run only when program at a time and all the processes of the system are allocated to that program. Later the more than one program at a time. The programs were required to specify all the resources in advance which they needed. Some operating system offers dynamic allocation resources, they request further resources after they start its execution. This lead to the problem of deadlock.

The resource may be either physical or logical. Physical resources are printers, tape drives, memory space, etc and logical resources are files, CPU, record stored in a database etc.

Fig: deadlock

Defination: Deadlocks are set of blocked processes each holding a resource and waiting to acquire a resource held by another process.

ii) Conditions for deadlock

A deadlock condition can arise if the following four conditions hold simultaneously in a system.

These conditions are:

- a) Mutual exclusion
- b) Hold and wait
- c) No – preemption
- d) Circular wait

- a) **Mutual exclusion:** A resource can be used by only one process at a time, if another process request that resource the requesting process must be delayed until the resource has been released.
- b) **Hold and wait:** A process must be holding at least one resource and waiting to acquire additional resources that are currently being held by other process.
- c) **No – preemption:** Resources cannot be taken from the process because resources can be released only voluntarily by the process holding them.
- d) **Circular wait:** A set of waiting processes like, $p_0, p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n$. must exist such that p_0 is waiting for a resource held by p_1 , p_1 is waiting for a resource held by p_2 and p_2 is waiting for a resource held by p_3 and so on. Finally p_n is waiting for a resource which is held by p_0 .

iii) Deadlock prevention

For a deadlock to occur each of the four condition must hold by ensuring that atleast one of these conditions can't hold, we can prevent the occurance of a deadlocks. Deadlock prevention can be explained under following headings:

- a) **Mutual exclusion:** the mutual exclusion condition must hold for non – shareable resources. An effort should be made to prevent mutual exclusion. This is possible by making all shareable resources.
Example: if several processes want to access read only file at the same time, they can be granted simultaneously. In this case there is no need of mutual exclusion. But few resources which can not change from non-shareable to shareable resources.
- b) **Hold and wait:** To ensure that hold and wait condition can never occur in the system we must guranter that whenever a process request a resource it does not hold any other resources.
Example: To take printout of the file you first request to disk, then you get and release it, then you request the printer to print the file you will get it and use it.
- c) **No-preemption:** To ensure that this condition doesn't happens preemption of resources should allowed for this we use a protocol i.e if a process that is holding a resource, request another resource that cannot be allocated to that process immediately. All the resources which are being held by that process are preempted. The process will

now wait for the resource allocation to those for which it was already waiting.

- d) Circular wait: In order to prevent this condition to occur, resources can be number and made it compulsory that a process request a resource in increasing order.

Example: A process requesting a resource disk drive number will be allocated a disk drive only if its existing resource have number less than 2. This implies that a process having printer can acquire disk drive only when it release all other resources.

iv) Deadlock avoidance

Avoid actions that may lead to deadlock. It is very difficult to determine when a system is about to reach a state of deadlock simply because it is nearly impossible to predict what process will request which resource before it is released by another process. The most efficient way for avoiding deadlocks is to acquire additional information about how resources are to be requested i.e the operating system requires information about resource needs of the various processes in advance and use during its life time. With this additional information, it can decide for each request whether or not the process should wait. A deadlock avoidance algorithm dynamically examines the resource allocation state to ensure that a circular wait condition can never occur. The resource allocation state is defined by the number of available and deallocated resources and the maximum demand of the processes.

Deadlock avoidance include two type of algorithms:

- a) Resource allocation
- b) Banker's algorithm

- a) Resource allocation graph algorithm: A resource allocation graphs shows which resource is held by which process and which process is waiting for a resource of a specific kind. This algorithm uses the

resource allocation graph to determine whether the allocation of a particular resource leads to the formation of cycles in graph or not. If no cycle exists then the allocation of resource leaves the system in safe state.

Fig: safe state resource allocation graph.

Example: In addition to request edge and assignment edge, draw claim edge process P_1 to R_2 . A claim edge P_1 to R_2 indicates that process P_1 may request resource R_2 at sometime in future and this claim edge is represented by dotted lines. When a process P_1 request resource R_2 the claim edge P_1 to R_2 is converted to a request edge, when a resource R_2 is released the assignment edge P_1 to R_2 is reconverted to claim edge P_1 to R_2 . when a process P_1 request resource R_2 the request can be granted only if converting the request edge P_1 to R_2 to an assignment edge R_2 to P_1 does not result in formation of a cycle in the resource allocation graph. If no cycle exists then the allocation of the resource will leave the system in safe state. And if a cycle is formed then the allocation will put the system in an unsafe state. Therefore process P_1 will have to wait for its request to be satisfied.

Fig: unsafe state

b) Banker’s algorithm: the resource allocation graph algorithm is not applicable to a resource allocation system with multiple instances of each resource type. Banker’s algorithm is a deadlock avoidance algorithm. It is named so because the algorithm could be used in a banking system to ensure that banks never allocated its available cash in such a way that it could no longer satisfy, the needs of all its customers.

When a new process enters, the system it declare the maximum number of each instance of each resource type that it may need. When a user request a set of resources. The system must determine weather allocation of these resources will lead the system in a safe state or not. If it is safe the resource must wait until some other process releases the resources.

Data structures used to implement the banker’s algorithm are:

- 1) Available: it indicates the number of available resources of each type.
- 2) Maximum: defines the maximum elements of each process.
- 3) Allocation: defines the number of resource of each type currently allocated to each process.
- 4) Need: indicates the remaining resources of each process.

Example: A=10, B= 5, C=7.

Process	Allocation	Max. need	Available	Remain need
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	A B C	A B C	A B C	A B C
P1	0 1 0	7 5 3	3 3 2	7 4 3
P2	2 0 0	3 2 2	5 3 2	1 2 2
P3	3 0 2	9 0 2	7 4 3	6 0 0
P4	2 1 1	2 2 2	7 4 5	0 1 1
P5	0 0 2	4 3 3	7 5 5	4 3 1

Formulas: Remaining Need = Maximum Need – Allocation

Available = Total – Allocation

New Available = Available + Allocation

The banker's algorithm is a combination of two algorithms namely, safety algorithm and resource request algorithm. These two algorithms together control the processes and avoid deadlock in a system.

v) Deadlock detection

Deadlock detection algorithms are used to identify the presence of deadlocks in computer system. There are two algorithms for deadlock detection. These algorithms determine whether a deadlock has occurred in the system or not.

- a) Single instance of each resource type: This algorithm deals with the case when there is only one instance of each resource type.

An edge from P1 to P2 in a wait for graph implies that process P1 is waiting for the process P2 to release a resource that process P1 needs.

- b) Multiple instance of each resource type: This algorithm deals with the case when there are multiple instances of each resource type.

To explain this algorithm, we consider a system with 3 processes P1, P2, P3, and 2 resources R1 and R2. R1 has one instance and R2 has two instances.

vi) Deadlock recovery

Deadlock recovery can be performed in a number of ways. Once the deadlock has been detected in the system, the system should now be recovered from this state. This is because it will continuously exploit the performance of the system. If we don't remove deadlock then there is a possibility of total system failure. Recovering from a deadlock involves identifying the processes involved and releasing the necessary resources. There are two different methods used to recover from the deadlocked state:

- a) Process Termination
- b) Resource Preemption

- a) Process Termination: In this we can abort all deadlocked processes, abort one process at a time until a dead lock cycle is eliminated.
- b) Resource Preemption: preempting some resources from processes and give these resources to other processes till the deadlock cycle is broken.

vii) Conclusions

Deadlock is a set of processes wait indefinitely for events because each of events can be caused only by other processes in the set. Several In general, deadlock detection or avoidance is expensive. Deadlock avoidance and recovery may cause starvation problems. Deadlock avoidance requires prior information on how each process will be utilizing resources.

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